

Hopf Bifurcation Proof

- **Article:** Study on Fear-Induced Group Defense and Cooperative Hunting: Bifurcation, Uncertainty, Seasonality, and Spatio-temporal Analysis in Predator-Prey System
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Our proposed system is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dH}{dt} &= \frac{bH}{1 + \beta P} - d_1 H - \frac{rH^2}{K + K_1 H} - \frac{(h + \alpha P)HP}{1 + b_2 H + b_3 \beta H^2} \equiv F_1(H, P) = H f_1(H, P), \quad (\text{say}) \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= \frac{e(h + \alpha P)HP}{1 + b_2 H + b_3 \beta H^2} - d_2 P \equiv F_2(H, P) = P f_2(H, P), \quad (\text{say}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

By treating β as a variable parameter, let us write the characteristic equation of system (1) for the Jacobian matrix $J(E_I)$ as follows:

$$\lambda^2 - T(\beta)\lambda + D(\beta) = 0 \quad (2)$$

In this context, $T(\beta)$ and $D(\beta)$ represent the trace and determinant of the Jacobian matrix associated with the interior equilibrium point E_I , respectively. Noticing a transition in the sign of the real component of λ from negative to positive indicates a shift in stability for the interior equilibrium point E_I , thereby altering its status from stable to unstable. This transition results in a Hopf bifurcation [Kuznetsov *et al.*, 1998], which takes place when the characteristic equation (2) provides a pair of roots that are purely imaginary. Assuming that the purely imaginary roots are located at $\beta = \beta^{[H]}$, it follows that $T(\beta^{[H]}) = 0$ and $D(\beta^{[H]}) > 0$. This theorem establishes the presence of a Hopf bifurcation within system (1) at the point where $\beta = \beta^{[H]}$.

Theorem 1. (*Hopf-bifurcation Theorem [Murray, 2007]*). *If $T(\beta)$ and $D(\beta)$ are the smooth functions of β in an open interval about $\beta^{[H]} \in \mathbb{R}$ such that the characteristic equation (2) has*

- I. *A pair of imaginary eigen-values $\lambda = g_1(\beta) \pm ig_2(\beta)$ with $g_1(\beta)$ and $g_2(\beta) \in \mathbb{R}$ so that they become purely imaginary at $\beta = \beta^{[H]}$ and $\left[\frac{dT}{d\beta}\right]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} \neq 0$.*
- II. *The other eigen-value is negative at $\beta = \beta^{[H]}$. Then a Hopf-bifurcation occurs around $E_I(H^*, P^*)$ at $\beta = \beta^{[H]}$ (i.e., a stability changes of $E_I(H^*, P^*)$ accompanied by the creation of a limit cycle at $\beta = \beta^{[H]}$).*

Theorem 2. *System (1) exhibits Hopf-bifurcation around $E_I(H^*, P^*)$ at $\beta = \beta^{[H]}$, when $T(\beta^{[H]}) = 0$, $D(\beta^{[H]}) > 0$ and $\left[\frac{dT}{d\beta}\right]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} \neq 0$.*

Proof. At $\beta = \beta^{[H]}$, $T(\beta^{[H]}) = 0$, $D(\beta^{[H]}) > 0$, the characteristic equation has purely imaginary roots, i.e. $\lambda_1 = i\sqrt{D(\beta^{[H]})}$ and $\lambda_2 = -i\sqrt{D(\beta^{[H]})}$. Therefore, $\lambda_1 = g_1(\beta) + ig_2(\beta)$ and $\lambda_2 = g_1(\beta) - ig_2(\beta)$ are the roots of the characteristic equation (2) in any open neighbourhood of $\beta^{[H]}$, where $g_1(\beta)$ and $g_2(\beta)$ are real valued functions of β . Using Hopf-Bifurcation Theorem [Murray & Murray, 2003], we may say that the stability of system (1) switches through a Hopf bifurcation, provided the following transversality condition

$$\left[\frac{d}{d\beta}(Re(\lambda_i(\beta)))\right]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} = \left[\frac{dg_1(\beta)}{d\beta}\right]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} \neq 0, \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2.$$

is satisfied. Let us put $\lambda(\beta) = g_1(\beta) + ig_2(\beta)$ in equation (2), then we get,

$$(g_1(\beta) + ig_2(\beta))^2 - T(\beta)(g_1(\beta) + ig_2(\beta)) + D(\beta) = 0$$

Now, differentiating both sides w.r.t. β we get,

$$2(g_1(\beta) + ig_2(\beta))(g_1(\beta) + ig_2(\beta)) - T(\beta)(g_1(\beta) + ig_2(\beta)) - \dot{T}(\beta)(g_1(\beta) + ig_2(\beta)) + \dot{D}(\beta) = 0$$

Now comparing the real and imaginary components on both sides, we get;

$$(2g_1 - T)g_1 - 2g_2g_2 - \dot{T}g_1 + \dot{D} = 0 \Rightarrow X_1g_1 - X_2g_2 + X_3 = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$(2g_2)g_1 + (2g_1 - T)g_2 - \dot{T}g_2 = 0 \Rightarrow X_2g_1 + X_1g_2 + X_4 = 0 \quad (4)$$

where, $X_1 = (2g_1 - T)$, $X_2 = 2g_2$, $X_3 = (\dot{D} - \dot{T}g_1)$, $X_4 = -\dot{T}g_2$. Now solving equations (3) and (4) we get,

$$g_1 = -\frac{(X_1X_3 + X_2X_4)}{X_1^2 + X_2^2} \quad (5)$$

At $\beta = \beta^{[H]}$. Now two cases arise :

Case I: When $g_1 = 0$, $g_2 = \sqrt{D}$ then, $X_1 = 0$, $X_2 = 2\sqrt{D}$, $X_3 = \dot{D}$ and $X_4 = -\dot{T}\sqrt{D}$. Hence from (5) we get,

$$[g_1]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} = \left[\frac{dg_1(\beta)}{d\beta} \right]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{dT(\beta)}{d\beta} \right]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} \neq 0$$

Case II: When $g_1 = 0$, $g_2 = -\sqrt{D}$ then, $X_1 = 0$, $X_2 = -2\sqrt{D}$, $X_3 = \dot{D}$ and $X_4 = \dot{T}\sqrt{D}$. Hence from (5) we get,

$$[g_1]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} = \left[\frac{dg_1(\beta)}{d\beta} \right]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} = -\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{dT(\beta)}{d\beta} \right]_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} \neq 0$$

Therefore, $\frac{d}{d\beta}(Re(\lambda_i(\beta))) \Big|_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} = -\frac{(X_1X_3 + X_2X_4)}{X_1^2 + X_2^2} \Big|_{\beta=\beta^{[H]}} \neq 0$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $T(\beta^{[H]}) = 0$, $D(\beta^{[H]}) > 0$.

Hence, theorem 2 is proved using theorem 1.

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References

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